

Teaching in the New Normal: Voices of Physical Education Teachers

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Abstract

This descriptive phenomenological study design explored the physical education teachers' experiences in handling major courses in Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) in the new normal. Twelve (12) physical education teachers were purposively selected to be the informants of the study. Data were gathered utilizing open-ended interview guide questions through one-on-one interviews via online meeting platforms. There were three (3) major themes that emerged in the study, to wit: (1) the teaching practice, (2) the attitude, and (3) the challenge. The data revealed that physical education teachers experienced various encounters in applying new teaching practices in the new normal that were significantly influenced by their attitude in response to the significant challenges confronting them. They have developed innovative teaching approaches to meet the demands of teaching Physical Education major courses in the new normal. Thus, it is recommended that physical education teachers will undergo pedagogical and technological training. Further, that the school administrators develop a curriculum fitted to the new normal setting and come up with a solution to solve internet connectivity problems.

Introduction

Teaching physical education (PE) amidst COVID-19 pandemic is not a simple undertaking, especially in giving instructions and assisting students when they are not in close proximity to the teacher. Several studies reported that teaching physical education in an online class does not provide sufficient education benefits to the students because the teacher and the students are physically and spatially separated (Yu & Jee, 2020; O'Brien et al., 2020; Filiz & Konukman, 2020). The implication of producing quality learning for students in an online learning delivery of physical education is still uncertain. Accordingly, higher education institutions (HEIs) need to ensure that physical education's intended learning outcomes are still achievable even during the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, conducting PE classes online posed several concerns and challenges to teachers, such as utilization of ICT and multimedia materials, students' attentiveness, internet connectivity, and many more.

Physical Education is an integral part of the school curriculum in Southeast Asia. With the 2015 ASEAN integration, the region is facing many challenges to realize its slogan – “One vision, one identity, one community.” School PE programs and extracurricular activities that are well-planned, organized, and efficiently implemented may benefit the community. It can develop productive and engaged citizens, provide social stability, generate economic advantage, enhance the community's identity, and build a healthier and improved community (Dudson, Cummings, & Fraser, 2012). Physical Education plays an essential role in the ASEAN education system's ability to carry out its slogan.

Moreover, physical well-being should not be put aside particularly amidst Covid-19 pandemic. Physical activities and sports are essential to keep the balance, especially in these trying times. Physical Education and regular exercise must continue to be promoted. Despite proposed recommendations to temporarily remove some subjects including physical education (PE), most educators, school administrators, and lawmakers fought for its retention in the national curriculum for higher education despite of the restrictions imposed during the pandemic.

In other countries, physical education is required, and its status differ from one state to another (Hardman, 1998; Eurydice, 2013; Klein & Hardman, 2007; Puhse & Gerber, 2005). According to Kirk (2010), the concept of PE is determined by society's views, attitudes, and ambitions toward it. However, this might lead to disagreements concerning the subject's nature, even with its importance in human growth as acknowledged since the 19th century. Priorities for the topic have shifted over time all around the globe (IOM, 2013). Following the work of authors such as Metzler (2005) in the United States, Kirk (2010) in the United Kingdom, during (2005) in France, and Bonaventure (2007) in Belgium, three overall phases of PE can be identified. These phases include: a long hygienic phase, influenced by Swedish and German gymnastics, up to the 1960s; a sport-centered phase, during the last third of the twentieth century; and a phase, since the turn of the millennium, increasingly focused

on health outcomes. Sallis and McKenzie (1991) noted that PE should concentrate on two key goals: preparing children and adolescents for a lifetime of physical activity (PA), and engaging them in physical activity throughout physical education. Tappe and Burgeson (2004) agreed that physical education should play a key role in encouraging kids to live active lives. PE instructors were identified as the pillars of a school's steps to address this social problem.

In the Philippine law, as stated in Section 2 of Republic Act (R.A.) 6847-The Philippine Sports Commission Act and Article XIV Section 19, it is the policy of the State to promote physical education; encourage and sustain the development of sports in the country to foster physical fitness, self-discipline, teamwork, and excellence for the development of a healthy and alert citizenry (Education, Science and Technology, Arts, Culture, and Sports of the 1987 Philippine Constitution). The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) streamlined physical education in the country with the CHED Memorandum Order No. 23, Series of 2011. Physical Education, as a discipline, therefore plays an important role in human development. It offers an opportunity to develop skills, discipline, confidence, leadership, and to carry fundamental democratic values.

Furthermore, the main goal of PE in schools is to provide an academic subject that will help the learners become physically active. In other words, it aims to produce an active population that adheres to the chosen exercise regimen. These individuals voluntarily perform their workouts because they are motivated, and the activities themselves are part of their preferences. They are self-regulating, a behavioral concept described by Stosny (2011) as the ability to act in the long-term best interest, consistent with the most profound set of values. Consequently, adherence to physical activities and exercise could be the best indicator to check whether the PE program in schools impacted the lives of the learners.

The shift from physical to virtual teaching has prompted the PE teachers to deal with online learning in the new normal for the academic year 2020-2021. Further, teachers need to employ new teaching methodologies in physical education major courses to address the need of virtual teaching. Hence, this study aimed to explore the experiences of the physical education teachers handling major courses in Physical Education virtually. Findings of this study may help in recommending future virtual or online approaches that would respond to the needs of teaching Physical Education major courses in the new normal.

Philosophical Stance

A philosophically examined view of the study is very essential. It becomes a guiding principle or perspective in this study, hence the foundation of this research. The following philosophical assumptions in terms of ontology, epistemology, axiology, rhetoric and methodology are the philosophical underpinnings that this study is examined and adhered to.

Ontology is the philosophical study of the nature of reality. Reality is multiple, as seen through many views. This questions the nature of reality of the physical education teachers' experiences handling major courses in the tertiary education institution (TEIs) in the new normal. It is the philosophical examination of the nature of educational reality and the possibility of divergent perspectives of what is known in education. Crotty (1998) asserts that all knowledge and meaningful reality are related to human practices, constructed from interactions between the human beings and their world and the development transmitted within an essentially social context. Technology or online pedagogies is the breadth and depth of access to education. Online pedagogies have been a trademark in higher education that the co-location of professors, students, and resources in time and space is the sine qua non of education. Through ontological perspective, it assumes that the phenomenon of using technology or virtual pedagogies in physical education would contribute to rich outcomes of learning realities from the interactions and experiences of the physical education teachers teaching major courses in the region's higher education institutions. The researcher accounts various perspectives as themes emerged in the study.

Epistemology is concerned with the philosophical study of knowledge grounded upon in someone's belief as something to be true (Oliver, 2010). This is subjective evident from the physical education teachers. The researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself and the physical education teachers' informants. On the other hand, according to Sharp (2009), what counts in this perspective is the academic knowledge and how it is obtained. Snape and Spencer (2003) cited that the epistemological stance is central to the choice of methodology concerning its purpose and goals since research by nature is all about seeking and generating new knowledge. With this, the study dwelt on the physical education teachers' experiences handling major courses in the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). It sought to explore on how these teachers understand and find meaning in teaching or delivering the course contents through online modalities. The researcher relies on quotes

as evident from the physical education teachers who collaborate and spend time in the field with their fellow PE teachers.

Axiology is the philosophical study of judgments and values. The researcher noted that research is value-laden and that biases in the analysis of data obtained from physical education teachers are evident. It is engaged in assessing the role of the researcher's value in all the stages of the research study. This philosophical stance primarily emphasizes the aims of the research and focuses on what is being valued in the research study. Online teaching pedagogies have been valued as it revolutionizes the entire education system; in the new normal online teaching is required in the learning process. From this perspective, this study explored the experiences of the physical education teachers handling major courses in the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the new normal with the view of recommending virtual modalities that can be adapted in teaching the PE major courses and are responsive to the needs in the new normal. The researcher explores the narrative's ideals and compares his interpretation with the opinions of the physical education teachers.

Methodology is a systematic planning or action about social reality (Strauss and Corbin (1998). The researcher employed inductive reasoning, investigated the issue in context, and utilized an emerging design to examine physical education teachers' experiences with major courses in the new normal. This study employed different methods to establish the study's rigor. A phenomenological inquiry attempts to deal with inner events or experiences not carefully examined in everyday life (Merriam, 2002). Methodologically, this study utilized a Husserlian descriptive phenomenology where it used a method of different steps in analyzing data through Colaizzi's qualitative data analysis. Another method employed is the process of bracketing before the data gathering procedure. This philosophical stance is adhered to by this study to describe the phenomenon being studied from a series of processes and methods. The researcher works with particulars before generalizations, describe the study's context, and continually revises questions from the physical education teachers' experiences.

Rhetoric patterns are ways of organizing information. Exploring the physical education teachers' experiences using an online Learning Management System (LMS) is the essence of this phenomenological study. In this research, explaining and describing the experiences of PE teachers handling major courses were the primary data being reviewed and analyzed. This study explored the physical education teachers' experiences handling major courses in the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the new normal with the view of recommending virtual modalities that can be adapted in teaching PE major courses and are responsive to the new needs of the new normal. The researcher is not omniscient but instead reports what the reality is through the eyes of the physical education teachers.

Domain of Inquiry

This study explored the physical education teachers' experiences handling major courses in the Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) in the new normal. It answered the question: *What are the lived experiences of Physical Education teachers handling major courses in Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) in the new normal?*

Review of Related Literature

The National Association for Sports and Physical Education (NASPE, 2007) noted that physical education teachers were divided on their view of the feasibility of Online Physical Education (OLPE) courses. According to the official NASPE website, physical education instructors are split on the practicality of online physical education (OLPE). The official NASPE view was that OLPE was a neutral learning approach, and its influence on learning would reveal whether the delivery strategy was good or not. Because of the purported negative impacts on learning, some people still doubt the legitimacy of OLPE as a viable educational alternative to face-to-face PE training. Many physical education instructors still believe that face-to-face training is the best way to ensure proper knowledge and skill development.

Moreover, many individuals, including political and official representatives, question whether or not OLPE should even be offered to students. On the other hand, E-Learning students at home generally lack the social interactions necessary for interplay between peers. Without interaction, the social-emotional aspects of the PE curriculum can be challenging to address.

Teachers and students may utilize the International Society for Technology in Education's (ISTE) technology standards. In addition, the National Council for Accreditation of Teacher Education (NCATE) and the National Association for Sport and Physical Education (NASPE) have set standards for technology integration in physical education teacher education programs. NASPE produced a policy statement in 2009 advocating the use of technology in physical education (Mears, Hansen, Fine, Lawler, Mason, & Richardson, 2009).

It was distinguished that PE used several technologies to increase K-12 students' activity levels and skill development. Technology is becoming more accessible in K-12 schools, and PETE programs must help teachers model technology-rich teaching (Castelli and Fiorentino, 2008). Despite the potential for improved instruction, there is evidence that physical education instructors are less likely than their subject-matter counterparts to employ technology (Vahey& Crawford, 2002). Teaching interns teaching physical education do not feel that they are prepared and equipped to incorporate technology in PE classes (Liang, Walls, Hicks, & Clayton, 2006).

NASPE established four recommendations for the usage of instructional technology in physical education to encourage PE teachers to become technology savvy: (1) it is projected to be an instrument to increase instructional efficacy, (2) is projected to enhance effective instruction, and not to replace it, (3) it should offer opportunities to all of students, and not just a few, (4) it can be used an effective tool for tracking students' data related to standards-based curricular goals (Mears et al., 2009, pp. 2-4). PE teacher candidates should utilize information technology to increase their knowledge, individual and professional productivity, according to the (NASPE). To examine the present state of technology utilization into PETE efforts, a goal and clear meaning of technology must be studied.

Although physical education teachers identified key elements that lead to success in online instruction, online courses cannot guarantee a better quality of training. Still, they can be regarded as a powerful tool for education purposes (Yotovska, Asenova&Slavov, 2018).

Notably, online learning environments offer the opportunity to create and integrate various learning resources and multiple assignments. In terms of study motivation, a standard view amongst participants was that online courses should support interaction and collaboration, foster self-regulation in their learning process, and include self-assessment forms. Drawing on concepts of university pedagogy (Biggs & Tank, 2011), participants should be encouraged to take responsibility for their learning progress. In teaching and learning, both in web-based and traditional classroom learning, it is essential that the learner adds value to their learning outcome and expects success in achieving it – two key factors that make students want to learn something (Biggs & Tank, 2011). Therefore, the expectations of online courses should be clearly defined and provide flexibility in how and when to complete course assignments.

The considerable opposition of education professionals to the training model and teaching modality given in Silva's (2019) research must be recognized; hence, the concept of the reflective curriculum, where practice and theory would walk so close together that it would be impossible to separate them. Consequently, it would be ideal for future PE professionals' professional development, both in person and through distance learning, enabling us to integrate what is taught with what is needed in the classroom. Distance learning allows for the sharing of experiences, the expansion of multiple intelligences and collective memory, the expansion of vocabulary from the great initiation to reading, and the experience of asynchronous and synchronous collective exchanges for Physical Education teacher preparation. Finally, since professional recognition and training quality are based on the student's profile and competence, the development and re-signification of new information make learning more relevant in the virtual world.

Methodology

Research Design

The design employed in this study is phenomenological approach. It utilized descriptive phenomenological design to explain the lived experiences of the physical education teachers in the higher education on their experiences in online learning. The intent to understand the use of online learning as relevant in the new normal is consistent with the study of their lived experiences. The design is centered on examining the depths of human experiences of physical education teachers through descriptions that they will share and provide.

Phenomenological research in professional teaching fields generally agrees on a few fundamental criteria. It indicates that the approach to developing a phenomenological technique should be flexible and adaptable to the phenomena under investigation (Crotty, 1998; Giorgi 1997; Pollio, Henley, & Thomson, 19917, Valle 1998. This study concentrates on “Giorgi’s situated structural descriptions”. Giorgi regards such descriptions as essentially incomprehensible. Giorgi’s is a 'pure' phenomenology, describing objects of consciousness by phenomenological reduction to arrive at scientific essences.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in six state universities, two sectarian universities and three non-sectarian universities offering a Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) program in the Visayas region, Philippines. The focus of this study was the physical education teachers teaching the major courses at the state universities in Cebu, Negros Oriental, Palompon Leyte, Baybay, Leyte, and Iloilo City; two sectarian and one non-sectarian universities in Cebu City; two non-sectarian universities in Dumaguete City and Tagbilaran City in the province of Negros Oriental and Bohol. The interviews were conducted virtually due to the pandemic.

Key Informants

Twelve (12) physical education teachers handling the major courses in the first semester, the academic year 2020-2021 were purposively selected to constitute the participants. They were selected using the following criteria: (a) must be a regular faculty, teaching at least three (3) years of the College of Teacher Education (CTE) and currently teaching the major courses in the identified schools in the first semester, academic year 2020-2021 and (b) must currently engage in the new normal set up of online learning management system. The criteria were based on the necessity to gather information about their experiences teaching PE major courses in online learning modalities and elaborate their thoughts based on the course content. Identified physical education teachers could express their point of view; thus, they can provide relevant information needed to draw out meaning from their experiences. Their willingness to participate in the study was ascertained and they were given ample of time to share their experiences and feelings during the interview.

Research Instrument

The researcher was the main research instrument in this phenomenological study since it was the researcher who transcribed the responses of the key informants. Consequently, the researcher ascribed the meanings of the statements given by the key informants and was responsible for the data analysis in analyzing the formulated meanings and constructing themes from the responses of the key informants in the flow of the interview.

The key informants were also considered vital instruments as they are the source of information in analyzing their lived experiences. This study used an interview guide to obtain necessary information or data from the physical education teachers. The interview questions were open-ended to grasp the in-depth clarification of discussion among the key informants of the study. Experts have validated the interview questions before it was used for the interview. These questions were framed into three parts: preliminary questions, lead questions, and wrap-up questions. Preliminary questions were questions that set up the mood of the interview. The preliminary asked the impressions of the teachers on online learning or learning management system. Lead questions dealt with the inquiries on using the online management learning system, their accessibility, application, and instruction. It further asked about their experiences. Lastly, the wrap-up questions summarized the whole interview and sought clarity on some points that might be misunderstood in the interview process. Key informants were asked further if there was something that they would like to add or share.

Data Collection Procedure

Before the conduct of the interview, approval of this research was sought from the university head. After which, approval from the target higher educational institutions participants was sought. Coordination from the college dean's office or department chairperson of each institution was also coordinated to get the number of participants following the set criteria.

Before the interview, consent was sought from the participants to participate in the study willingly. Virtual orientation was conducted to give instructions and overview on the interview process. They were also asked to sign a consent form; the audio recording was one of the activities that needed approval from the participants. After the interview, the recorded data were transcribed. Transcripts were carefully read and analyzed to grasp the exact statements from the participants.

Data Analysis Technique

Phenomenological methodology attempts to explicate the meaning structures developed through the experiences of the person or persons being questioned. This study accounts for the lived experiences of the prospective teachers in online learning in the new normal. Through virtual interviews, transcripts were analyzed with Giorgi's (1997) thematic analysis method and summarized one methodological approach to explicating experience. Giorgi's six (6) step process of phenomenological data analysis were the following (1) intuitive/holistic understanding of the raw data, (2) forming a constituent profile, (3) forming a thematic index, (4) searching the thematic index, (5) arriving at an extended description & (6) synthesis of extended descriptions.

Rigor of the Study

The rigor or the trustworthiness of this study and the transparency of the conduct of this research is essential to the efficacy and reliability of the findings (Connely, 2016). Accurate selection of informants, following data saturation, ethical consideration, in-depth interview and lengthy engagement with the informants, and triangulation of the data sources are some of the specific practice methods used in the sampling and collection process to increase the rigor and trustworthiness of qualitative studies (Johnsons et al., 2020). The truth value, applicability, consistency, and neutrality of the data obtained were used to guarantee rigor (Cypress, 2017). As a result, this demonstrates the study's rigor and trustworthiness.

Ethical Considerations

This study's ethics approval was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee (REC) from a state university. The participants were informed of the purpose of the study, how it would be conducted, the extent of their involvement and the benefits and risks for them. They were also made aware of their liberty to participate or not in the study and their freedom to withdraw from the study with no repercussions. The participants were assured that their participation or nonparticipation and withdrawal from the research and their responses would have no bearing on their professional lives. To uphold the principles of privacy, anonymity and confidentiality, the name of participants were not mentioned in any part of the study. The prospective participants were also asked for their consent to participate in the study.

Results and Discussion

About the Informants

Table 1 presents the profile of the informants. It shows the name of the participants in pseudonyms, the sector/university, no. of years in teaching, and the learning management system used in their university.

Table 1.
Profile of the informants

Participant	Higher Educational Institutions	No. of Years in Teaching	Residence/ Address	Learning Management System Used
A	Participant Private (Non-Sectarian) University	5	Dumaguete City	University Online Learning
B	Participant State University	20	Dumaguete City	Google Meet / Classroom
C	Participant State University	8	Cebu City	Google Meet / Classroom
D	Participant State University	7	Baybay, Leyte	Google / Moddle
E	Participant Private (Sectarian) University	5	Cebu City	Zoom / Quipper Philippines
F	Participant Private (Sectarian)	3	Cebu City	Canvas / Google
G	Participant Private (Non-Sectarian) University	3	Cebu City	Kite Academy / Moddle
H	Participant Private (Non-Sectarian) University	18	Tagbilaran City	Google
I	Participant State College	3	Palompon, Leyte	Google
J	Participant State University	20	Iloilo City	Google
K	Participant State University	3	Cebu City	Google
L	Participant State University	3	Ormoc City	Google

As shown in the table, the study was participated by twelve Physical Education teachers teaching major courses in the new normal in the Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) offering Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) in the Visayas region, Philippines. Seven of which were from a state university / college and the other five informants are from a private university. All the informants are teaching Physical Education major courses in

the Academic Year 2020-2021 and experienced new modalities of teaching-learning set-up. The seven PE teachers from state university utilized Google Classroom and Google Meet as their learning management system. On the other hand, teachers from private universities have their own learning platforms, like Moodle, Canvas, Quippers, etc. The significant statements were identified and formulated meanings were deduced from the transcription.

“Teaching in the New Normal: Voices of Physical Education Teachers”

After the one-on-one virtual interview, the data were then transcribed and analyzed. The data were analyzed using thematic analysis with the assistance of the NVIVO software. The study yielded three core themes; first, is the teaching practice, second, is the teacher’s attitude and third, is the challenges in the teaching.

Theme 1: Teaching Practice

Teaching practice refers to the ways physical education teachers handling major courses in the tertiary higher education in the new normal. This theme generally entails the teaching practices of physical education teachers during instruction. This theme is categorized into three subthemes and these includes (1) Utilization of both synchronous and asynchronous (2) Use of ICT and Multimedia in the Teaching-Learning process, and (3) Assessments.

Subtheme 1.1 Utilization of synchronous and asynchronous

Synchronous learning allows students to engage with the teachers and their classmates simultaneously, while asynchronous offers learners the flexibility to study in a self-paced manner. This subtheme indicated that teachers who are teaching Physical Education major courses utilized both the synchronous and asynchronous methods. Teachers have the option to use synchronous classes when conducting lectures or discussions. One informant shared that:

“We only discuss the details during our synchronous meeting. So, video option, like that other staff that can be done during asynchronous wherein they can watch during their convenient time”.

Likewise, the teachers also have the option to use asynchronous classes like the used of printed modules that are delivered to the students. Another informant shared that:

“During the first semester it was also a struggle because we have to prepare both platforms. So, we need to print out, we need to create printed modules that is intended for the students and will be delivered to the students for free. And as well as create also virtual classrooms. So, printed module students are separate, and also those students in online.”

This subtheme revealed that Physical Education teachers utilized synchronous and asynchronous online classes in their teaching practices. Synchronous online instruction creates immediate social engagement, helps build a sense of community and clarifies misconceptions (Dawson, 2006; Giesbers et al., 2013, 2014; Hrastinski et al., 2010, as cited in the article of Stanford Graduate School of Education, 2020) In contrast, asynchronous instruction is more flexible. This allows students more time to explore and engage with material (Davidson-Shivers et al., 2001 as cited by Stanford Graduate School of Education, 2020) and provides access to a wider range of students.

Incorporating synchronous and asynchronous online classes is beneficial in attaining learning goals and covering all the contents (Stanford Graduate School of Education, 2020). This result also supported the study of Nasri et al. (2020), which revealed that teachers engaged in synchronous classes and asynchronous online learning because of technical difficulties.

Subtheme 1.2 I integrated ICT and Multimedia

The second subtheme is about the use of ICT and Multimedia in their classes. This entails the use of technological tools and resources to communicate and teach students with the combination of animated graphics, video, and sound to appeal to the students for entertainment and learning in physical education. Teachers made use of videos from Youtube and for evaluation, the teachers asked their students to create a video demonstrating the skills they have learned. An informant stated that:

“I urge my students to use the video, but then how do I share, how do I demonstrate. Since I don’t have that prepared video for myself doing the skills, I go to the YouTube because there are so many materials in the YouTube that you could use.”

Moreover, teachers made use of YouTube, but it is their decision on which videos to watch to make sure that all contents and information in the videos being used are credible. One informant voiced out that:

“For this semester sir I’m using Google Meet in terms of my instructions and also YouTube. I let them use YouTube. In my end I’m the one who record the video. I’m the one who demonstrates so that they will also learn”.

The second subtheme emphasized the integration of ICT and Multimedia. ICT, as Techopedia (2020) defines is the technology responsible for handling communications processes, including telecommunication media broadcasting, systems on intelligent building management, processing of audiovisual and transmission systems, and network-based control and functions in monitoring. On the other hand, Multimedia is defined by Webster’s dictionary as a technique of combining text and sounds in expressing an idea in which various mediums are involved.

In this case, Physical Education teachers used ICT and multimedia in their teaching practices. Williyanto’s (2020) study supports technology utilization and found out that teachers used technology in this new normal of education. Video-based instruction was also used by the teachers for further teaching the course. Some teachers made their videos, and others utilized videos on social media like YouTube. The same result is also found in the study of Nasri et al. (2020), in which, according to the study, teachers maximized the use of videos in teaching Physical Education. Rasmitadila et al. (2020) also highlighted using videos in teaching in the new normal. Videos were self-made and were taken on some social media, which also supported the result of the study.

Subtheme 1.3 I use varied assessment tools

Varied assessment tools were used to measure students’ performance in physical education. This subtheme entailed the assessment being utilized by teachers on their students. Teachers have noted that the students are graded based on their outputs and practical examination. Likewise, in grading the student the teachers gave considerations like giving extensions on the submission of outputs. One informant highlighted that:

“Akong bases for assessment nila kay ilaha ng outputs ug practical exam, musubmitsila. Mao akong bases para makagradekonilasailang submission. And a matter of sympathy kay lageangmgabataari sir kay man gyudingon tang makaafford so we give them extension. Musubmit man pudsila, diligent man pudsila”. (My bases for assessment are their submitted outputs and practical examination. Those are my bases to grade them. And a matter of sympathy, I gave them extension of deadlines. They submit to the extended deadline, and the students were diligent)

Moreover, the students are informed and aware of the criteria being used by the teacher on the performance task of the student. Also, another informant added that:

“With the use of criteria ngaakonggihatagatleast aware sila kung giunsanakopaghimoilanggrado. Actually, advantage pudsatao as PE teacher kay performance. Di bayanamalimbongang performance kay sa written napwederamagsinundugaysila. So medyodirigyud ta bawaisa performance task. Rubrics and criteria akonggibasehan”. **(With the use of criteria that I gave, the students were aware how do I compute grades. It is an advantage for us PE teacher because of performance based. It is impossible to be deceived in the performance compared to the examination where cheating is evident. So most of the part were based on performance task. I used rubrics and criteria.)**

Physical Education teachers highlighted the importance of assessment in teaching. Planning, discussion, consensus building, reflecting, measuring, analyzing, and improving based on data and artifacts obtained regarding a learning aim are all part of the assessment process (Martell and Calderon (2005). A variety of activities are included in the assessment, including testing, performances, project assessments, and observations (Orlich, Harder, Callahan & Gibson, 2004). The study revealed that teachers utilized the students' output in assessing their performances. This supported the study of Pace and Petit (2020), which emphasized the importance of authentic assessment to be included in the students' performance. In addition, the result showed

the importance of sympathy in teaching which teachers manifest. This contradicted the study of Varea & Gonzalez (2020), which found that sympathy was difficult to extend in online classes.

To sum up theme 1, the PE teachers' practices in teaching in this new normal include the utilization of synchronous and asynchronous online learning; integration of ICT and multimedia; and the utilization of various assessment tools.

Theme 2. The attitude

Attitude is defined by how physical education teachers think and feel about the instruction. This theme is about the Physical Education teachers' different attitudes in teaching major courses in the new normal. This theme is divided into two subthemes; first, is the flexibility and second, is the motivation.

Subtheme 2.1 I am flexible

This theme is about the flexibility of teachers. This refers to the personality trait of the physical education teachers that describes how the teacher can cope with changes in circumstances and think about problems and tasks in novel ways. With the current situation, teachers must be flexible and adaptive to the changes, develop technical skills in using technology and considerate to their students.

“A teacher should be flexible, flexible in different kind of set ups may it be virtual, or personal. So, a teacher should be flexible. And then, developed a technical skill, we should be techy for this time, we are here to explore, especially to the elders, old teachers.”

Likewise, teachers must compromise and be considerate with their students. This would include giving extensions with the submissions of activities and outputs.

“I even have student last semester who most of the family members are Covid positive. Even deadline I stretch that one just to give to the students because their incubation period is 14 days.”

It is never a question of the incapability among PE teachers teaching online, even though there is a lot of negative feedback coming from the teachers themselves (Hebecci et al., 2020). Nevertheless, teachers' flexibility played a significant role in this new normal of teaching. The Cambridge dictionary defines flexibility as the ability to adapt easily to changes and other situations. In this case, being flexible in their instruction and how they handle their students helped the Physical Education teachers in their profession. Moreover, being technology-driven is one of the skills highlighted in the teachers' teaching experiences. This is supported by Ludeman et al. (2009) as cited by Toquero (2020), who stated that technology literacy is essential in online teaching.

Subtheme 2.2 I am motivated

This subtheme described the teacher's motivation in teaching. This entails the processes that account for the physical education teacher's intensity, direction and persistence of efforts towards attaining a goal. With the current predicament, the teachers are driven to teach physical education to their students in promoting health and well-being.

“What makes me motivated, I know the feeling of not being an active person, so, I really feel that if I will not go outside, I feel like I get sick. So, I am more motivated to teach physical education even in online setups since I want everybody to become healthy, fit, even in their houses at the same time it will divert their attention from any bad news.”

Likewise, teachers as much as possible find ways to make lessons engaging and motivating.

“For PE teachers, there are a lot of videos online that you can refer on for you to make PE as much as possible engaging, motivating to students. So, you can just watch on online and you can actually refer on that one. An on my end, even I have given certificates to students during the end of the semester that they have complied or completed Physical Education.”

The informants' responses revealed why Physical Education teachers continue to teach despite the difficulties. Physical Education was institutionalized to produce an active and alert citizenry (Article XIV, Section XIX of the Philippine 1987 Constitution). This motivates teachers to continue teaching and to have healthy and active living (CHED Memo 23, series of 2021). Even though the giving of an instruction is online, teachers are still motivated to work and committed to achieving learning outcomes. This claim contradicts the findings of O'brian et al. (2020), which stated that in online teaching, learning outcomes are challenging to meet.

Moreover, extrinsic and intrinsic motivation encourage teachers to work hard, stay diligent, and make the class lively. The study by M. Ruma (2013) stated that when the employee engages in a task because they delight in the work, motivation occurs. As a result of the association between motivation and performance, management and organizational psychology research hold that highly motivated people are significantly more likely to be high performers.

To sum up the second theme, the attitude of a Physical Education teacher significantly affects the teaching-learning process. Flexibility in instruction and motivation towards teaching ensured success in online teaching.

Theme 3. The challenge

Challenge is defined as a new or difficult task that tests the physical education teacher's ability and skill. The third theme described the challenges confronted by the teachers. It theme is categorized into three subthemes; (1) I cannot do physical demonstration, (2) I am unsure if my students are paying attention, and (3) I have problems with my internet connection.

Subtheme 3.1 I cannot do a physical demonstration of lessons

This subtheme discusses the challenges of the teachers who are unable to perform practical demonstrations. This serves to teach or reinforce psychomotor skills by allowing the physical education teacher to provide an observable model for a complete motor skill or specific performance criteria within a skill. Physical education lessons include the execution of physical activities which requires physical demonstration, but with today's educational mode of learning, it is hard for teachers to guide and instruct their students.

“Actually, the difficulties with the PE teachers, so one of the major difficulties we are facing right now or the challenges major problem is the, for me, is the implementation or giving the instruction to our students especially this is physical education movement enhancements skills, so, the guidance, the proper execution, for example, subject exercise.”

Similarly, given the current situation and limited resources, teachers believe that teaching skills such as swimming, which should be done in the water with pupils, is difficult.

“This is the first time that I have handle aquatics in an online class. As I was saying this is a skills class. When I teach face to face, we go to the water with the students. Every new skill that I teach, I give a demonstration, and this is what lacking in an online class. I cannot give my physical demonstration. I cannot give them the tips or the importance of some skills why they to do this.”

Physical Education is known to be a performance-based course. The majority of the lessons are more on skills acquisition and movement activities. Teachers are expected to demonstrate and scaffold to assure effective transfer of learning and safety. This study revealed that teachers had difficulty of performing demonstration teaching because of the current setup. Physical Education teachers in an online class struggled to teach the course due to its nature. It is already an identity of Physical Education to move and let the body physique function (Varea& Gonzalez-Calvo, 2020).

Furthermore, aside from the burden of demonstrating, it is also a significant burden of Physical Education teachers on how to give instructions and how to assist, knowing that they are not in close contact with the students. Goad and Jones (2017) highlighted that it is still a contentious discussion if Physical Education online classes can produce well-rounded learners considering the nature of the course. This further supports the study of O'Brien et al. (2020) stating that it is challenging to meet the learning outcomes in an online class.

Moreover, it was highlighted in the teacher's responses that the lack of facilities contributed to their teaching difficulty. This supported the claim of Tria (2020), which stated that learning PE online is ineffective because of

the lack of facilities at home. It is a stressful journey knowing that there is lack infrastructures (O'Brien et al., 2020)

Subtheme 3.2 I am unsure if my students are paying attention

This subtheme emphasized teachers' uncertainties of students' attention, absorption of lessons and instructions given in class since it affects their class performance. This exhibits a lack of attention of students to the class. These notions were evident as respondent said that:

"We can actually see how they perform during synchronous and asynchronous by the mere fact when they submit their videos. Let us say for instance if they are not listening to our previous discussion then most probably this will affect their output videos."

Furthermore, some students are currently employed, and teachers are hesitant whether they are still attending their activities in class.

"I learned that some students are full-time employees, they work full time and full time also as a student, so you know they cannot serve two masters at the same time. So, lack of focus, lack of resources, lack of concentration, and it goes back to the character of the student. So those were the challenges that I encounter. Technological, professional and personal"

Students and teachers are in two different learning environments in an online class. Teachers cannot directly check whether the students are still paying attention, which will lessen their interaction (Orhan&Beyhan, 2020). It will not just affect the teaching-learning process but also the student's performance and outputs. The teachers emphasize that there is no assurance that students are still learning in online classes. Monitoring is a dilemma (Varea, 2020); that's why many claims say it is ineffective, as stated in the study of Hebebcı et al. (2020), because of the lesser interaction and communication. The same is stated by Adnan et al. (2020), who found that online classes were ineffective in third-world countries like Pakistan and the Philippines.

Teachers also revealed the challenge in terms of the lack of resources, lack of concentration and lack of students' commitment. Moreover, students are not purely students during these online classes because they might also have other priorities. This is also a burden on the teacher knowing that a lack of focus and resources will also affect their performance (Marciaga, 2020). According to Pace (2020), some students' access to gadgets is difficult. These findings also agreed with Hebebcı et al. (2020) claim which highlighted the impact of lack of resources, infrastructure, and facilities in the teaching-learning process.

Subtheme 3.3 I have problems with internet connectivity

Unreliable internet connectivity is one of the challenges encountered by the physical education teachers. This final subtheme highlights the difficulties instructors faced with their internet connections. This is particularly difficult when teaching skills in synchronous classes.

"During the deepening, actually this is my observation only if you're going to teach skills online during synchronous meetings, I would like to say that it would be hard to say for some students especially on some areas who difficulty on their connection, especially on their bandwidth is very slow. They really have a hard time of catching up what you are going to perform"

Similarly, not only teachers but also students are having problems with their internet connections due to the several places that are experiencing connectivity troubles.

"I really find difficulty in some ways especially because of connections. That's one area that I have encountered so many problems because not all of my students have a should I say good connection in their localities, so that's one area also"

The Philippines has the slowest internet connectivity in Southeast Asia (Akamani, 2017, cited in Tria, 2020). So, it was expected that internet connection would be one of the challenges in the new mode of learning. The findings showed that it is not only the students who are challenged with their connections but also the teachers. Physical Education teachers find it hard to teach skills in an online class because not all students have access to it. This greatly affected the students, like how one caught up with their missing topics or activities.

Moreover, Garcia and Weiss (2020) stated that the problem with internet connection is evident and experienced both by the students and teachers. It was highlighted in the study of Mercier et al. (2020) that internet connectivity is a major struggle, especially for those students living in rural areas.

To sum up, the third theme highlighted the significant challenges teachers experienced; the difficulty of skill demonstration in a synchronous class, teachers' uncertainties about whether their students still attend their classes and the problems with the internet connectivity.

Implications and reflections

Physical Education teachers experienced various encounters in applying new teaching practices in the new normal that were significantly influenced by their attitude in response to the significant challenges they encountered. They have developed innovative teaching approaches to meet the demands of teaching Physical Education major courses in the new normal.

Recommendations

It is suggested that physical education teachers undergo pedagogical and technological training. It is also recommended that the school administrators develop a curriculum fitted to the new normal setting and come up with a solution to solve internet connectivity problems.

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